

NAVIGATING DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION: EXPLORING THE NEXUS BETWEEN DIGITAL LEADERSHIP AND JOB SATISFACTION

Tolga ALTINTAS

Merve Nur YARANGÜME**

İsa İPCİOĞLU***

* Corresponding Author, Research Assistant, Bilecik Şeyh Edebali University, Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, Business Administration, tolga.altintas@bilecik.edu.tr, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0763-6195>.

** Bilecik Şeyh Edebali University, Institute of Social Sciences, mervenuryarangume811881@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-0740-3158>.

*** Prof. Dr., Bilecik Şeyh Edebali University, Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, Business Administration, isa.ipcioglu@bilecik.edu.tr, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6912-3290>.

ABSTRACT

The global impact of digitalization is a phenomenon that affects businesses in a multitude of ways. It is imperative that businesses undergo digital transformation across all business processes, with leaders playing a pivotal role in ensuring this transformation occurs. It is hypothesized that those in leadership positions will gain a competitive advantage by implementing digital transformation across the entire organization. This study explores the interplay between digital leadership and job satisfaction, emphasizing the pivotal role of leaders in navigating organizational transformation in the digital age. By synthesizing recent literature, the research identifies a positive correlation between digital leadership practices and employee satisfaction. Digital leadership, characterized by technological expertise and human-centric approaches, fosters innovation, enhances employee motivation, and mitigates resistance to change. Despite its relevance, the relationship remains underexplored, with limited empirical evidence addressing mediating variables and contextual factors. This review aims to enrich the academic discourse by highlighting practical implications for leadership development and future research directions.

Keywords: Digital Transformation, Digital Leadership, Job Satisfaction, Organizational Transformation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The advent of digital technologies has instigated a profound transformation in organizational structures and processes. As businesses adapt to this evolving landscape, digital leadership has emerged as a cornerstone of effective digital transformation. Leaders equipped with the skills to integrate technological advancements with organizational strategies play a crucial role in fostering innovation, efficiency, and workforce adaptability (Ordu & Nayır, 2021; Goran et al., 2017). Digital transformation, while offering substantial opportunities, also presents challenges that demand visionary and adaptable leadership (Hensellek, 2020).

Digital leadership represents a shift from traditional leadership paradigms, emphasizing technological acumen alongside interpersonal skills. The

integration of digitalization into a business increases the communication of that organization at the administrative level (Dijkstra, J., 2020). Leaders in this domain are tasked not only with adopting innovative technologies but also with guiding their teams through cultural and operational changes necessitated by digitalization (Sow & Aborbie, 2018; Westerman et al., 2014). Leadership has been identified as a key factor influencing the perception of organizational policies and their subsequent impact on employee job satisfaction levels (Ferris & Fandt, 1989). Their ability to balance technological proficiency with a people-centered approach often determines the success of transformation initiatives. In addition to driving technological change, digital leaders must also address employee concerns, foster inclusivity, and ensure that organizational goals align

with employee aspirations (Hensellek, 2020; Cortellazzo et al., 2019).

Amid the rapid pace of digitalization, job satisfaction remains a cornerstone of organizational success. Defined as the degree to which employees feel fulfilled and motivated in their roles, job satisfaction directly impacts performance, retention, and overall organizational health (Locke, 1969; Spector, 1985). Historically, leadership styles such as transformational, participatory, and ethical leadership have been linked to higher levels of job satisfaction (Bogler, 2001; Barker & Nelson, 2005). However, the rise of digital leadership introduces new dynamics into this relationship, as digital transformation reshapes not only workflows but also the expectations and experiences of employees (Şahin et al., 2020; Topçuoğlu et al., 2023).

The integration of digital tools and platforms has heightened the importance of effective leadership in managing employee expectations and mitigating resistance to change. Digital leaders engage in activities at three distinct levels. They endeavour to cultivate and reinforce the personal competencies of their personnel, provide their subordinates with opportunities to expand their knowledge base, facilitate consensus within the team, and disseminate external information to their followers (Zupancic et al., 2018).

Digital leaders who demonstrate empathy, adaptability, and a clear vision can enhance job satisfaction by aligning organizational processes with employee needs (El Sawy et al., 2016; Artüz & Bayraktar, 2021). Conversely, the absence of strong digital leadership can lead to dissatisfaction, manifesting as resistance to technological adoption, reduced morale, and decreased productivity (Haddud & McAllen, 2018).

Despite the growing recognition of digital leadership's importance, the interplay between digital leadership and job satisfaction remains underexplored in the literature. In the context of the digital age, the relationship between leaders and employees is of paramount importance in order to achieve favourable outcomes in the domain of digital leadership. However, existing studies have primarily

focused on the technical aspects of digital transformation, with limited attention to its human dimensions. Investigating this relationship is essential to understanding how leaders can foster a positive work environment amidst digital upheaval (Benitez et al., 2022; Pasolong et al., 2021).

This study synthesizes existing literature to examine the relationship between digital leadership and job satisfaction. The succeeding sections delve into the conceptual foundations of digital leadership and job satisfaction, followed by an analysis of their interrelationship. The discussion highlights empirical findings and identifies gaps in the literature, concluding with practical implications and recommendations for future research. By addressing these aspects, the study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the critical role digital leadership plays in shaping employee satisfaction within digitally transformed organizations.

2. DIGITAL LEADERSHIP

The term "leader" is traditionally defined as an individual who directs and inspires others toward achieving specific goals (Webster, 1994). Leaders play pivotal roles in organizations, driving motivation, facilitating change, fostering effective communication, and influencing employees' job satisfaction and organizational commitment (Tengilimoğlu, 2005).

While some argue that leadership qualities are innate, others emphasize the significant role of life experiences, particularly during formative years, in shaping an individual's leadership potential (Gün & Aslan, 2018). Leadership styles have evolved over time to address the demands of dynamic environments and technological advancements. Successful leaders exhibit adaptability and innovation, tailoring their approaches to align with contemporary organizational challenges (Bildik, 2009).

Traditional leadership paradigms—autocratic, bureaucratic, democratic, and charismatic—dominated for decades. However, the modern workplace has seen the emergence of ethical, transformational, participatory, and, more recently,

digital leadership styles, reflecting the increasing complexity and interconnectedness of the global landscape (Arslan et al., 2024).

The shift toward new leadership paradigms is not merely a reaction to changing organizational needs but also a response to broader societal transformations. The rise of knowledge economies, globalized workforces, and the integration of artificial intelligence and automation have necessitated leaders who can navigate complexity, foster innovation, and promote adaptability among employees.

2.1. The Emergence of Digital Leadership

The concept of digital leadership has emerged as a response to the unique challenges posed by the digital age. The transition from analog to digital technologies has resulted in profound transformations over the past seventy years, marking the advent of the digital age. This transition initiated what is now termed the Information Age, characterized by the rise of computers and associated software in the latter half of the 20th century (Ordu & Nayır, 2021).

Technological innovations underpinning this shift, which began during the Industrial Revolution, have culminated in significant structural changes that now define modern industries and societies (Wilson III, 2004). The introduction and proliferation of digital technology have had immediate and lasting impacts on nearly every aspect of people's lives globally, from communication to professional practices and beyond (Benson, 2018).

Despite periods of economic uncertainty and global crises, many international platforms have maintained a commitment to digital transformation, recognizing the economic and operational benefits of digitalization (Ordu & Nayır, 2021). Digital transformation is increasingly viewed as a strategic imperative for businesses, offering competitive advantages to organizations that successfully navigate the transition (Arslanhan Memiş, 2018). In today's digitally driven world, businesses that embrace digital innovation stand to gain significant advantages, including enhanced efficiency, improved

customer engagement, and expanded market reach (Bolte et al., 2018; Sheninger, 2014).

The pace of digital transformation has accelerated dramatically in recent years, particularly in response to the global SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, which underscored the critical need for technological adaptation (Yıkılmaz, 2021). Organizations were compelled to adopt digital strategies at unprecedented rates, revealing both the potential benefits and inherent challenges of this transition. One of the most difficult aspects of digital transformation lies in individual adaptation. The process is inherently time-consuming and often requires a combination of organizational alignment, leadership commitment, and external conditions that facilitate natural progression (MaryAnne, 2018).

2.2. The Role of Leadership in Digital Transformation

Digital leadership refers to a style of leadership that integrates technological expertise with traditional leadership competencies, emphasizing the ability to guide organizations through periods of technological and cultural change (Rudito & Sinaga, 2017). It involves aligning people with novel digital processes through motivation, influence, and a strategic vision (Meier, 2017).

Digital leadership is a pivotal component of organizational success in the digital age. By integrating technological expertise with strategic vision and human-centric approaches, digital leaders drive transformation, foster innovation, and ensure long-term organizational resilience (Shah & Patki, 2020). As the global business landscape continues to evolve, the role of digital leaders will remain critical in shaping the future of work and achieving sustainable success.

Leadership plays an essential role in the success of digital transformation efforts. The process necessitates a clear vision, strategic guidance, and the ability to inspire organizational alignment. Leaders act as catalysts for change, ensuring that both technological and human dimensions of transformation are addressed. Studies emphasize the critical role of leaders in motivating employees, reducing resistance to change, and fostering an

innovative culture that embraces digital processes (Ordu & Nayır, 2021; Sow & Aborbie, 2018). Without effective leadership, organizations may struggle to realize the full potential of digital transformation efforts. Furthermore, leadership has the capacity to minimise errors and enhance individual knowledge and growth opportunities for members (Braun et al., 2013).

2.3. The Rise of Digital Leadership

The rapid digitization of industries has redefined leadership paradigms, giving rise to digital leadership—a style that integrates technological expertise with adaptive and innovative approaches. Digital leaders are instrumental in guiding organizations through the complexities of digital transformation, leveraging technology to enhance performance and foster innovation.

Digital leadership is characterized by the strategic use of digital tools and systems to optimize operations, drive growth, and create competitive advantages. Leaders in this domain act as visionaries and coaches, facilitating digital transformation while ensuring alignment with organizational goals (Aslan, 2021; Klein, 2020). Mihardjo et al. (2019) describe digital leadership as an organizational competency that integrates advanced communication, computing, and telecommunications technologies. Likewise, it is also employed to describe a novel generation of leaders who deploy digital tools and inspire their employees to embrace digitalisation (Zeike et al., 2019). These leaders bridge the gap between technological advancements and employee capabilities, fostering a culture of continuous learning and adaptation.

Digital leadership is not limited to technological proficiency; it also entails emotional intelligence, ethical decision-making, and strategic vision. Effective digital leaders understand the human dimensions of technology adoption, ensuring that employees feel supported, valued, and empowered throughout the transformation process.

In essence, digital leadership can be defined as a style of leadership that leverages information technology to unite and mobilize a following, promoting the intelligent and productive use of technology (Asri &

Darma, 2020). Digital leaders demonstrate leadership across the entire value chain, aligning their actions with the latest developments in their field (Bowen, 2021). They play a pivotal role in bridging the gap between technological innovation and human adaptability, ensuring that employees are equipped to navigate the complexities of digital transformation (Cortelazzo et al., 2019). A digital leader's responsibilities extend beyond the implementation of new technologies; they also include fostering an inclusive culture that transcends barriers such as religion, language, and race, thereby ensuring collective alignment with organizational objectives (Winston & Patterson, 2006).

Traditional models of leadership are often insufficient in addressing the dynamic challenges of the digital age. Consequently, organizations must adopt alternative paradigms that prioritize collaboration, technological integration, and strategic adaptability (Malakyan, 2019). Compared to traditional leaders, digital leaders exhibit a greater proclivity for collaboration and demonstrate a stronger orientation towards leveraging technology for business success (Hearsum, 2015; Temelkova, 2018).

Digital leadership, as defined by Şahin et al. (2020), combines digital tools and resources with strategic and managerial thinking to achieve organizational objectives in a rapidly changing world. El Sawy et al. (2016) further describe digital leadership as a strategic approach that ensures organizational success by addressing environmental factors and leveraging digital tools.

2.4. Addressing Challenges in Digital Leadership

Digital leaders face unique challenges, particularly in addressing the apprehensions of employees regarding digital transformation. A study by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF, 2017) found that 60% of employees fear job losses due to digitalization and automation. Digital leaders must address these concerns by fostering a balance between technological advancements and workforce well-being. Ensuring that employees feel supported and valued is critical to minimizing resistance and maximizing engagement throughout

the transformation process (Teichmann & Hüning, 2018).

In addition to managing workforce concerns, digital leaders must navigate the risks and opportunities associated with technological integration. They are responsible for implementing innovative approaches, driving productivity, and ensuring ethical considerations are prioritized in decision-making processes (Baker & Nelson, 2005; Hensellek, 2020).

2.5. Characteristics of Effective Digital Leaders

Effective digital leaders possess a distinct set of attributes that enable them to navigate the complexities of the digital age successfully. In a study conducted on digital leadership, the characteristics deemed essential for a digital leader were identified as honesty and transparency, exemplary conduct, a clear vision, fairness, guidance, individual interest, openness to innovation, and a high level of knowledge (Toduk, 2017). In another study addressing the concepts associated with digital leadership in the context of management sciences, it is asserted that digital leadership is linked to a range of factors, including the characteristics of leaders, an innovative approach to business, success, and a technology adaptation model (Ercan Önbiçak & Akkoyun, 2022).

In a further study of digital leadership, the concept of digitalization was examined, as well as its impact on the characteristics of leaders and the skills and competencies required of those in positions of authority. The majority of these were found to be conceptual in nature (Özmen et al., 2020). The literature on digital leadership commonly identifies the following characteristics as being particularly prevalent among those who can be considered digital leaders:

Technological Proficiency: A deep understanding of digital tools and platforms is essential for making informed decisions and driving innovation (Mert, 2021).

Vision and Strategic Thinking: Digital leaders must articulate a clear vision for the future, aligning

organizational efforts with long-term objectives and market trends (Daud et al., 2021).

Adaptability: The ability to respond to changing circumstances and embrace new challenges is crucial in navigating the dynamic digital landscape (Promsri, 2019; Kane et al., 2019).

Collaboration and Communication: Digital leaders foster teamwork and ensure open communication across organizational hierarchies, facilitating alignment and engagement (Çelik Şahin et al., 2020; Kellogg et al., 2020).

Cultural Intelligence: Recognizing and valuing diversity within globalized work environments is essential for fostering inclusivity and innovation (Miller, 2018).

Soft Skills: Digital leadership is a combination of soft skills, including ethical responsibility and agility (Herold, 2016).

2.6. The Impact of Digital Leadership

Digital leadership significantly influences organizational success by enhancing operational efficiency, fostering innovation, and driving employee engagement. By integrating digital technologies, organizations can streamline workflows, reduce human error, and meet evolving customer expectations (Freitas Junior et al., 2020). Digital leaders also play a critical role in fostering a positive organizational culture, motivating employees, and driving productivity.

Furthermore, digital leadership enhances an organization's competitive advantage by enabling it to capitalize on global market opportunities. Digital leaders are adept at identifying emerging trends, aligning organizational strategies with market demands, and navigating the complexities of global competition (Jäckli & Meier, 2020).

2.7. Challenges and Barriers

Despite its potential, digital leadership presents challenges. Many organizations struggle with the implementation of digital transformation initiatives due to leadership deficits, resistance to change, and insufficient stakeholder engagement (Correani et al., 2020). Effective digital leaders must possess the

knowledge, experience, and interpersonal skills necessary to overcome these barriers and drive successful transformation efforts (Haddud & McAllen, 2018).

A key distinction between leaders and employees in digital organizations lies in their approach to transformation (Altıntaş & İpcioğlu, 2024). While employees adapt to new technologies, leaders are responsible for orchestrating these changes, demonstrating digital competencies, and ensuring alignment with organizational objectives (Matt et al., 2015).

3. JOB SATISFACTION

The term "job satisfaction" is often used interchangeably with similar concepts, marking its origins in academic studies dating back to the 1920s (Gafa & Dikmenli, 2019). The concept was formally introduced in 1931 through organizational research conducted by Fisher and Hanna. Locke (1969) later theorized that employees exhibit greater happiness and productivity when assigned tasks aligned with their character and competencies. He described this alignment as "job satisfaction" and associated it with the notion of fulfilling and agreeable work.

While the term first emerged in the 1920s, the broader implications of job satisfaction, particularly its positive influence on employees' physical and mental well-being, became evident by the 1940s. These findings reinforced the concept's importance in organizational contexts, leading to continued exploration and development (Spector, 1985). By 1971, Churchill and colleagues advanced the field by publishing seminal research on measuring job satisfaction, directly linking it to job definitions and the work environment (Zhu, 2013).

Job satisfaction can be conceptualized as an individual's overall attitude and behavior toward their profession. It embodies the internal peace and contentment experienced by employees in relation to their roles. Positive attitudes toward work reflect job satisfaction, whereas negative attitudes indicate job dissatisfaction (Üçüncü, 2016). This construct can also be described as the emotional state arising from the congruence between an individual's work-life conditions and their positive perception of their

occupation (Ugboro & Obeng, 2000). Additionally, job satisfaction encapsulates the benefits derived from one's role, fostering a harmonious and joyful work environment through effective collaboration with colleagues (Bingöl, 1997).

The attainment of job satisfaction is linked to personal success and internal serenity (Kaliski, 2007). Conversely, job dissatisfaction often precipitates adverse outcomes, such as absenteeism and an inclination to resign, leading to substantial organizational costs (Çarıkçı & Çelikkol, 2009). Job dissatisfaction can significantly affect organizational performance, reducing employee motivation and productivity. It may also increase employee turnover and intra-organizational conflicts, ultimately resulting in considerable financial and operational losses for the organization (Şimşir & Seyran, 2020).

3.1. Factors Influencing Job Satisfaction

Several organizational factors contribute to job satisfaction, with the nature of the job itself being a critical determinant. The degree to which employees enjoy their roles and perceive them as aligned with their abilities and preferences is fundamental to their overall satisfaction (Altundaş, 2000). In the literature, wage levels are emphasized as a direct correlate of job satisfaction (Andrews, 2003).

Working conditions also play a pivotal role. Elements such as occupational health, safety, and overall workplace comfort are significant contributors to job satisfaction (İşcan & Sayın, 2011). Effective organizations strive to create environments that prioritize employee well-being by safeguarding against environmental hazards, ensuring quiet workspaces, using safe machinery, and maintaining a radiation-free workplace (Bingöl, 2003).

Promotion opportunities represent another influential factor. The potential for career advancement within an organization has been shown to enhance both job satisfaction and motivation. Crucially, promotion processes must be perceived as fair and equitable (İşcan & Sayın, 2011). Career progression not only increases employees' sense of responsibility but also positively impacts their social environment and professional standing (Robbins, 2001).

Moreover, the quality of interpersonal relationships within the workplace significantly influences job satisfaction. Positive interactions among employees facilitate equitable workload distribution and foster a sense of social cohesion, thereby enhancing productivity and maximizing employee happiness and motivation (Sabuncuoğlu, 2001).

3.2. Perspectives on Job Satisfaction

Numerous scholars have offered definitions of job satisfaction, emphasizing its multifaceted nature. Bullock conceptualized job satisfaction as an attitude shaped by a synthesis of various work-related experiences (Çalışkan, 2005). The emotional and character-driven dimensions of job satisfaction are further highlighted in the literature, underscoring the individual variability in its perception (Üçüncü, 2016).

Eren (2001) proposed that job satisfaction encompasses not only financial compensation but also the fulfillment derived from harmonious relationships with colleagues and the successful execution of one's responsibilities. Weiss (2008) posited that job satisfaction is an objective evaluation rather than a mere emotional response, aligning with Liess and Judge's (2004) assertion that it reflects an individual's attitudes toward their occupational role.

Davis (1988) defined job satisfaction as the emotional response—either happiness or unhappiness—experienced by employees in their professional capacities. Statt (2004) further elaborated on this idea, describing job satisfaction as the extent to which individuals feel gratified by the rewards they receive for their work. George & Jones (2008) emphasized that job satisfaction encompasses the aggregate of feelings associated with occupational roles, influenced by factors such as job characteristics, interpersonal relationships, and communication with superiors.

Mullins (2005) observed that perceptions of job satisfaction vary across individuals, shaped by their internal experiences and emotional states. Aziri (2008) described job satisfaction as an emotional state arising from the perception that one's job meets both material and psychological needs. This sentiment is vital for both employees and

organizations, as high levels of job satisfaction correlate with increased productivity, openness to change, and reduced turnover. For instance, during the COVID-19 pandemic, employees with high job satisfaction demonstrated resilience and adaptability to rapidly changing workplace dynamics, maintaining their commitment to their roles (Hamzah et al., 2021; Marbawi et al., 2022; Muniroh et al., 2021).

3.3. Consequences of Job Dissatisfaction

Job dissatisfaction, at the individual level, manifests as withdrawal behaviors, emotional distress, and instability. Employees experiencing dissatisfaction may display unfriendliness, preoccupation with personal concerns, and diminished focus on their work. Prolonged dissatisfaction can lead to psychological disorders (Üçüncü, 2016).

At the organizational level, job dissatisfaction results in adverse outcomes such as high turnover rates, increased absenteeism, frequent errors, and strained employer-employee relations. These challenges contribute to declining workplace performance and significant financial losses for the organization. In addition, dissatisfaction exacerbates workplace conflicts and undermines overall team morale, posing long-term risks to organizational success (Üçüncü, 2016).

4. THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DIGITAL LEADERSHIP AND JOB SATISFACTION

The relationship between digital leadership and job satisfaction is a burgeoning area of inquiry, reflecting the transformative impact of technology on leadership dynamics and employee experiences (Al-Hussami, 2008). Digital leaders, by integrating technological expertise with empathetic practices, influence various aspects of employee satisfaction. Digital leadership represents a transformative approach to management, integrating technology, innovation, and employee engagement. By fostering supportive and efficient workplace environments, digital leaders enhance job satisfaction, drive performance, and contribute to organizational success. Empirical evidence underscores the universal relevance of digital leadership across industries, regions, and cultural contexts

(Cortellazzo, 2019). As organizations continue to embrace digital transformation, the role of digital leaders will become increasingly critical. Their ability to inspire, innovate, and adapt will not only shape the future of work but also ensure sustainable organizational growth in an ever-changing global landscape (Kane et al., 2015).

4.1. Leadership Styles and Their Impact on Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction, a critical factor in organizational success, is deeply influenced by leadership styles and behaviors. Leaders significantly shape their employees' attitudes, motivations, and perceptions of their work environment (Radulescu et al., 2020). Research has consistently demonstrated that positive perceptions of leadership are associated with higher levels of job satisfaction (Yalçıntaş & Eren, 2017). For instance, when leaders adopt positive behavioral changes, their actions tend to foster greater satisfaction among employees (Karaduman, 2002).

People-oriented leadership approaches, as highlighted by Bogler (2001), are particularly effective in enhancing job satisfaction, as they prioritize employee well-being and engagement. Similarly, ethical leadership fosters satisfaction by aligning business goals with staff encouragement and support (Bello, 2012; Brown et al., 2005; Zhou et al., 2015). Leadership behaviors characterized by paternalism, such as providing protection and support to employees, also correlate positively with job satisfaction (Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008; Anwar, 2013).

Ethical leadership, which emphasizes fairness, integrity, and respect, has been consistently linked to enhanced job satisfaction. Leaders who adopt ethical principles inspire trust and loyalty among employees, creating a positive workplace culture (Bello, 2012; Brown et al., 2005; Zhou et al., 2015). Similarly, paternalistic leadership, characterized by protective and nurturing behaviors, meets employees' emotional and professional needs, thereby boosting satisfaction levels (Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008).

Transformational leaders, who encourage innovation, adaptability, and competitiveness, create an environment where employees develop positive

attitudes toward their roles, thereby enhancing job satisfaction (Bushra et al., 2011). Likewise, visionary leaders who mitigate employee uncertainties positively influence satisfaction levels (Yılmaz & Karahan, 2010). A dual focus on people- and task-oriented leadership has been identified as the most conducive to job satisfaction, as noted by Barker et al. (2007) and Önder (2010). This approach not only promotes financial performance but also bolsters non-financial outcomes, including organizational commitment and individual performance (Park et al., 2021).

4.2. Digital Leadership and Job Satisfaction: Empirical Evidence

The relationship between digital leadership and job satisfaction has been extensively studied across industries and regions. Research consistently demonstrates that digital leaders positively influence employee satisfaction by fostering supportive, innovative, and efficient workplace environments. For instance, Abbasov and Tolay (2021) and Artüz (2020) found that digital leadership enhances employee performance and satisfaction, particularly in organizations undergoing digital transformation. These leaders enable employees to achieve goals more effectively by reducing inefficiencies and creating collaborative, technology-driven environments.

Benitez et al. (2022) examined the impact of digital leadership on organizational innovation, finding that leaders who leverage digital platforms significantly enhance their firms' innovation capacity. Their study underscores the importance of digital leadership in fostering creativity, which, in turn, contributes to job satisfaction. Yusuf et al. (2023) provided further evidence of the positive relationship between digital leadership and employee performance. Their analysis revealed that effective digital leaders not only improve individual productivity but also create conditions that enhance employees' overall workplace experience.

4.3. Digital Leadership in Sector-Specific Contexts

Numerous studies highlight the transformative impact of digital leadership across various sectors.

Alfares and Banikhaled (2022) investigated the role of digital leadership in the healthcare industry, reporting significant improvements in employee performance and satisfaction. Similarly, Erhan et al. (2022) explored the textile industry in Turkey, concluding that digital leadership fosters innovative behaviors among employees, which contribute to higher satisfaction levels.

In public administration, Hanandeh et al. (2023) demonstrated the positive effects of digital leadership on business process performance and entrepreneurial motivation. Their findings emphasize the versatility of digital leadership in enhancing organizational outcomes, regardless of sectoral differences.

The education sector has also benefited from digital leadership. Srimata et al. (2019) found that school administrators practicing digital leadership positively influenced the school climate, leading to higher teacher engagement and satisfaction. Similarly, Tanucan et al. (2022) reported a strong correlation between digital leadership and job satisfaction among teachers, underscoring its relevance in fostering supportive and innovative educational environments.

4.4 Enhancing Job Satisfaction Through Digital Leadership

Digital leadership enhances job satisfaction by addressing key employee needs: efficient task management, opportunities for growth, and a positive work environment. Leaders who leverage digital tools and strategies enable employees to complete tasks with greater accuracy, reduced stress, and higher productivity. These outcomes contribute significantly to overall job satisfaction (Altınöz, 2008).

Research also highlights the role of digital leadership in fostering intrinsic motivation. Azzam et al. (2022) found that digital leaders positively influence employees' well-being, motivation, and performance, creating environments where individuals feel valued and engaged. Similarly, Sulistina and Darma (2023) reported that digital leadership enhances satisfaction by promoting collaboration, innovation, and adaptability.

In a study conducted by Antonopoulou et al. (2021), it was demonstrated that the highest levels of productivity and satisfaction are achieved when digital leadership is fully implemented. Topcuoglu et al. (2023) further emphasized the holistic impact of digital leadership. Their study revealed that employees under digital leaders not only experience greater job satisfaction but also report higher life satisfaction, illustrating the far-reaching effects of this leadership style.

4.5 Challenges and Opportunities in Digital Leadership

Despite its numerous benefits, digital leadership is not without challenges. Leaders must navigate rapid technological changes, address resistance to innovation, and ensure equitable access to digital tools and training. Effective digital leaders overcome these challenges by fostering a culture of inclusivity and continuous learning, ensuring that employees at all levels feel supported during the transformation process.

Kamaruddin et al. (2024) underscore the importance of leadership agility in addressing these challenges. Their study revealed that leaders who prioritize adaptability, transparency, and ethical decision-making foster higher levels of employee satisfaction and engagement, even in rapidly changing environments.

While existing research highlights the positive impact of digital leadership, further exploration is needed to understand its intersection with emerging trends such as artificial intelligence, remote work, and cross-cultural collaboration. Longitudinal studies could provide deeper insights into how digital leadership evolves over time and its sustained impact on employee outcomes.

Future research should also explore the mediating and moderating factors that influence the relationship between digital leadership and job satisfaction. Variables such as organizational culture, employee demographics, and industry-specific factors may shape the effectiveness of digital leadership practices.

5. CONCLUSION

This study underscores the critical role of digital leadership in enhancing job satisfaction within the context of digital transformation. By synthesizing theoretical insights and empirical evidence, it demonstrates that digital leaders, through their ability to align technological innovation with human-centric approaches, foster environments conducive to employee well-being and organizational success.

The importance of this subject cannot be overstated, particularly as organizations worldwide undergo profound changes driven by the rapid pace of technological advancement. In an era where digital tools and automation increasingly shape work environments, understanding how leadership adapts to and harnesses these technologies is paramount. Digital leadership emerges as a linchpin in navigating these complexities, serving as a bridge between technological imperatives and human needs. Leaders adept at integrating innovation with empathy not only ensure smoother transitions during digital transformation but also cultivate workplace cultures that prioritize employee satisfaction and retention.

A key takeaway is the multifaceted impact of digital leadership on employee satisfaction. Leaders who prioritize transparency, inclusivity, and skill development create a culture of trust and empowerment. These qualities are particularly significant in addressing challenges such as resistance to change and technological apprehension. Employees are more likely to embrace digital transformation when they feel supported and valued, reducing turnover and fostering long-term loyalty. By proactively addressing these challenges, digital leaders serve as catalysts for sustaining employee motivation and productivity in rapidly evolving workplaces.

This study is also significant because it brings much-needed attention to the interplay between leadership and digital transformation. Organizations are increasingly recognizing that technological upgrades alone cannot drive success; leadership that inspires and motivates employees is equally critical. Highlighting the strategies and behaviors of effective

digital leaders provides organizations with actionable insights to enhance both individual and organizational performance.

However, the study also highlights several gaps in the existing literature, which present exciting opportunities for further research. For instance, while the influence of digital leadership on job satisfaction is evident, the mediating roles of organizational culture, employee digital literacy, and technological infrastructure remain underexplored. These variables could significantly shape how digital leadership is perceived and its overall effectiveness. Additionally, longitudinal studies examining causal relationships are essential to understand the enduring impact of digital leadership on job satisfaction, particularly as organizations move from initial digital adoption phases to more advanced stages of digital maturity.

Another promising avenue for further exploration is the intersection of digital leadership with diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) initiatives. As workplaces become more diverse, understanding how digital leaders can create equitable and inclusive environments will be critical for fostering holistic organizational growth. This includes examining how leaders can leverage technology to address inequities, promote inclusive decision-making, and ensure equal access to digital resources and opportunities.

From a practical perspective, organizations must invest in developing digital leadership competencies. This involves not only technical training but also fostering soft skills such as empathy, adaptability, and collaboration. Leadership development programs should emphasize the importance of balancing technological expertise with human connection, enabling leaders to inspire trust and drive meaningful change. Furthermore, organizations should consider integrating digital leadership principles into their overall strategic frameworks to ensure alignment with long-term goals.

The implications of digital leadership extend beyond individual organizations, influencing broader societal and economic outcomes. By equipping leaders with the skills needed to navigate digital

transformation effectively, societies can better address challenges such as the digital divide, workplace automation, and shifts in labor market dynamics. Future research should therefore consider the macro-level implications of digital leadership, exploring its role in shaping sustainable and inclusive growth.

In conclusion, digital leadership represents a transformative force in modern organizations, bridging the gap between technological advancement and employee satisfaction. Its relevance will only grow as workplaces continue to evolve, characterized by new technologies, diverse workforces, and complex global challenges. The ability of leaders to adapt, inspire, and innovate will be the defining factor in achieving long-term organizational excellence. Future research should continue to explore this dynamic field, offering innovative strategies to enhance both leadership practices and employee experiences. By doing so, scholars and practitioners alike can contribute to building workplaces that are not only technologically advanced but also deeply human-centric, ensuring a harmonious and productive future for all stakeholders.

REFERENCES

Abbasov, A., & Tolay, E. (2021). Dijital liderliğin bireysel performans üzerindeki etkisi: Azerbaycan'da endüstri 4.0 teknolojilerini uygulayan bir firmada araştırma. *İzmir Yönetim Dergisi*, 2(1), 59-74.

Adams, J. S. (1963). Towards an understanding of inequity. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 67(5), 422.

Al-Hussami, M. (2008). A study of nurses' job satisfaction: The relationship to organizational commitment, perceived organizational support, and transactional leadership. *Journal Name*, 22(3), 286–295.

Altıntaş, T., & Ipcioğlu, I. (2024). Humble Leadership and Organizational Citizenship Behavior: Insights from Contemporary Research. *European Journal of Digital Economy Research*, 5(1), 19-28.

Altundaş, O. (2000). *Poliste stres ve iş tatmini*. AÜSBE, Erzurum.

Andrews, C. (2003). *Comparative analysis of management and employee job satisfaction and policy perceptions*. University of North Texas.

Antonopoulou, H., Halkiopoulos, C., Barlou, O., & Beligiannis, G. N. (2021). Associations between traditional and digital leadership in academic environment: During the COVID-19 pandemic. *Emerging Science Journal*, 5(4), 405-428.

Anwar, H. (2013). Impact of paternalistic leadership on employees' outcome – A study on the banking sector of Pakistan. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 7(6), 109-115.

Arslan, E. Y., Yeniçeri, E., & Ayan, Ş. (2024). Okul müdürlerinin etik liderlik davranışları ile öğretmenlerin iş tatmini arasındaki ilişki. *Ulusal Özgün Eğitim Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 2(1), 163-176.

Arslanhan Memiş, S. (2018). Dijitalleşmenin ekonomik boyutu. H. Aksu içinde, *Dijital dönüşüm yolculuk rehberi*. İstanbul: Pusula Yayıncılık.

Artüz, S. D. (2020). *Dijital liderlik uygulaması ile öğrenen örgüt ilişkisinin bireysel performansa etkisi*. İstanbul Ticaret Üniversitesi.

Artüz, S. D., & Bayraktar, O. (2021). The effect of relation between digital leadership practice and learning organization on the perception of individual performance. *İstanbul Ticaret Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 20(40), 97–120

Asri, A. A. S. M. A. N., & Darma, G. S. (2020). Revealing the digital leadership spurs in 4.0 industrial revolution. *International Journal of Business, Economics & Management*, 3(1), 93-100.

Aziri, B. (2008). *Human resource management, job satisfaction and motivation of employees*. Tringa Design.

Baker, T., & Nelson, R. E. (2005). Creating something from nothing: Resource construction through entrepreneurial bricolage. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 50(3), 329–366.

Bass, B. M., & Avolio, B. J. (1993). Transformational leadership and organizational culture. *Public Administration Quarterly*, 112-121.

- Bello, S. M. (2012). Impact of ethical leadership on employee job performance. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(11), 228-236.
- Benitez, J., Arenas, A., Castillo, A., & Esteves, J. (2022). Impact of digital leadership capability on innovation performance: The role of platform digitization capability. *Information & Management*, 59(2), 103590.
- Benson, L. E. (2018). Leadership skills in the digital age: Implications for university business schools. *Journal of Eastern European and Central Asian Research*, 5(2), 80-89.
- Bildik, B. (2009). *Liderlik tarzları, örgütsel sessizlik ve örgütsel bağlılık ilişkisi*. Gebze Yüksek Teknoloji Enstitüsü, Kocaeli.
- Bingöl, D. (1997). *Personel yönetimi* (3rd Ed.). Beta Yayıncılık.
- Bingöl, D. (2003). *İnsan kaynakları yönetimi* (5th Ed.). Beta Yayıncılık.
- Bogler, R. (2001). The influence of leadership style on teacher job satisfaction. *Educational administration quarterly*, 37(5), 662-683.
- Bolte, S., Dehmer, J., & Niemann, J. (2018). Digital leadership 4.0. *Acta Technica Napocensis-Series: Applied Mathematics, Mechanics, and Engineering*, 61(4), 637-646.
- Bowen, G. (2021). Digital leadership, ethics and challenges. In H. Jahankhani, L. M. O'Dell, G. Bowen, D. Hagan, & A. Jamal (Eds.), *Strategy, leadership, and AI in the cyber ecosystem: The role of digital societies in information governance and decision making* (23-39). Academic Press.
- Braun, S., Peus, C., Weisweiler, S. & Frey, D. (2013). Transformational leadership, job satisfaction, and team performance: A multi level mediation model of trust. *Leadership Quarterly*, 24 (1), 270-283.
- Brown, M. E., Trevino, L. K., & Harrison, D. A. (2005). Ethical leadership: A social learning perspective for construct development and testing. *Organizational Behaviour and Human Decision Processes*, 97, 117-134.
- Bushra, F., Usman, A., & Naveed, A. (2011). Effect of transformational leadership on employees' job satisfaction and organizational commitment in banking sector of Lahore (Pakistan). *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(18), 261-267.
- Cortellazzo, L., Bruni, E., & Zampieri, R. (2019). The role of leadership in a digitalized world: A review. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, Article 1938.
- Correani, A., De Massis, A., Frattini, F., Petruzzelli, A. M., & Natalicchio, A. (2020). Implementing a digital strategy: Learning from the experience of three digital transformation projects. *California Management Review*, 62(4).
- Çalışkan, Z. (2005). İş tatmini: Malatya'da sağlık kuruluşları üzerine bir araştırma. *Doğu Anadolu Bölgesi Araştırmaları*, 9-18.
- Çarıkcı, İ. H., & Çelikkol, Ö. (2009). İş-aile çatışmasının örgütsel bağlılık ve işten ayrılma niyeti etkisi. *Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, (9), 153-170.
- Çelik Şahin, Ç., Avcı, Y. E., & Anık, S. (2020). Dijital liderlik algısının metaforlar yoluyla incelenmesi. *Elektronik Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 19(73), 271-286.
- Daud, S., Wan Hanafi, W. N., & Mohamed Othman, N. (2021). Determinant factors for fourth industrial revolution (4IR) leadership attributes: An empirical study from Malaysia. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(9), 301-311.
- Davis, K. (1988). *İşletmede insan davranışı* (Tosun K., Trans.). İstanbul Üniversitesi İşletme Fakültesi Yayınları, No: 199.
- Dijkstra, J. (2020). *Digital leadership and firm performance: A meta-analysis*. University of Groningen.
- El Sawy, O. A., Kræmmergaard, P., Amsinck, H., & Vinther, A. L. (2016). How LEGO built the foundations and enterprise capabilities for digital leadership. *MIS Quarterly Executive*, 15(2), 141-166.
- Ercan Önbiçak, A., & Akkoyun, B. (2022). Dijital liderlik çalışmalarının yönetim bilimleri kapsamında incelenmesi: Nitel bir araştırma. *Malatya Turgut*

- Özal Üniversitesi İşletme ve Yönetim Bilimleri Dergisi, 3(2), 128-137.
- Eren, E. (2001). *Örgütsel davranış ve yönetim psikolojisi* (7th Ed.). Beta Basım Yayıncılık.
- Ferris, G. R., Russ, G. S., & Fandt, P. M. (1989). Politics in organizations. In R. A. Giacalone & P. Rosenfeld (Eds.), *Impression management in the organization* (143–170). Erlbaum.
- Freitas Junior, J. C., Cabral, P. M. F., & Brinkhues, R. (2020). Digital transformation: The gap between digital leadership and business performance. *ISLA 2020 Proceedings*.
- Fisher, V. E. & Hanna, J. V. (1931). *The dissatisfied worker*. New York: Mcmillan.
- Fisk, P. (2002). The making of a digital leader. *Business Strategy Review*, 13(1), 16-23.
- Gafa, İ., & Dikmenli, Y. (2019). Sınıf öğretmenlerinin iş doyumunu ve iş yaşamındaki yalnızlık düzeylerinin incelenmesi. *Ahi Evran Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 5(1), 60-75.
- George, J. M., & Jones, G. R. (2008). *Understanding and managing organizational behavior* (5th Ed.). Pearson/Prentice Hall.
- Goran, J., LaBerge, L., & Srinivasan, R. (2017). Culture for a digital age. *McKinsey Quarterly*, 3, 56-67.
- Gün, İ., & Aslan, Ö. (2018). Liderlik kuramları ve sağlık işletmelerinde liderlik. *Sağlık ve Hemşirelik Yönetimi Dergisi*, 5(3), 217-226.
- Hackman, J. R., & Oldham, G. R. (1976). Motivation through the design of work: Test of a theory. *Organizational Behavior & Human Performance*, 16(2), 250–279.
- Haddud, A., & McAllen, D. (2018). Digital workplace management: Exploring aspects related to culture, innovation, and leadership. *2018 Portland International Conference on Management of Engineering and Technology (PICMET)*.
- Hamzah, N. H., Nasir, M. K. M., & Wahab, J. A. (2021). The effects of principals' digital leadership on teachers' digital teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic in Malaysia. *Journal of Education and E-Learning Research*, 8(2), 216–221.
- Hanandeh, A., Altaher, A., Halim, M., Rezk, W., Mahfoudh, N., Hammouri, Q., & Darawsheh, S. (2023). The effects of digital transformation, digital leadership, and entrepreneurial motivation on business decision making and business process performance: Evidence from greater Amman municipality. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 7(2), 575-582.
- Hearsum, S. (2015). How to develop digital leadership capability. *Strategic HR Review*, 14(5).
- Hensellek, S. (2020). Dijital liderlik: Dijital çağda başarılı liderlik için bir çerçeve. *Medya Yönetimi ve Girişimcilik Dergisi*, 2(1), 1-15.
- Herold, G. (2016). Leadership in the fourth industrial revolution. *Stanton Chase Business Journals*, 22(12), 1–15.
- Herzberg, F., Mausner, B., & Snyderman, B. (1959). *The motivation to work*. New York: Wiley.
- İşcan, Ö. F., & Sayın, U. (2011). Örgütsel adalet, iş tatmini ve örgütsel güven arasındaki ilişki. *Atatürk Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Dergisi*, 24(4), 195-216.
- Jäckli, U., & Meier, C. (2020). Leadership in the digital age: Its dimensions and actual state in Swiss companies. *International Journal of Management and Enterprise Development*, 19(4), 293-312.
- Kamaruddin, M. J., Buchdadi, A. D., & Wolor, C. W. (2023). The influence of digital leadership and organizational culture through job satisfaction on employee performance of PT. *Pakistan Journal of Life and Social Science*, 22(1).
- Kaliski, B. S. (2007). *Encyclopedia of business and finance* (2nd Ed.). Thompson Gale.
- Kane G. C., Palmer D., Phillips A. N., Kiron D. and Buckley N. (2015), Strategy, Not Technology, Drives Digital Transformation, MIT Sloan Management Review and Deloitte University Press, 3-25.
- Kane, G. C., Phillips, A. N., Copulsky, J., & Andrus, G. (2019). How digital leadership is(n't) different. *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 60(3), 34-39.
- Karaduman, A. (2002). *Ekip çalışmasında liderin iş tatmini üzerindeki etkisi*. Erzurum Uni.

- Kellogg, K. C., Valentine, M. A., & Christin, A. (2020). Algorithms at work: The new contested terrain of control. *Academy of Management Annals*.
- Li, W., Liu, K., Belitski, M., Ghobadian, A., & O'Regan, N. (2016). E-leadership through strategic alignment: An empirical study of small- and medium-sized companies. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(11), 4619-4624.
- Locke, E. A. (1969). What is job satisfaction? *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance*, 4(4), 309-336.
- MacKenzie SB, Podsakoff PM., & Rich GA (2001) Transformational and transactional leadership and salesperson performance. *Journal of Academy of Marketing Science*, 29(2), 115-134.
- Malakyan, P. G. (2019). Digital leader-followership for the digital age: A North American perspective. In M. Franco (Ed.), *Digital leadership - A new leadership style for the 21st century*. Intech Open.
- Marbawi, M., Hamdiah, H., & Nurmala, N. (2022). Antecedents of competence, digital learning and the influence on teacher performance of senior high school. *International Journal of Engineering, Science and Information Technology*, 2(1), 152-157.
- MaryAnne, M. G. (2018). Digital strategy and digital transformation. *Research-Technology Management*, 61(5), 66-71.
- Maslow, A. H. (1943). A theory of human motivation. *Psychological Review*, 2, 21-28.
- Matt, C., Hess, T., & Benlian, A. (2015). Digital transformation strategies. *Business & Information Systems Engineering*, 57(5), 339-343.
- McGuinness, S., Pouliakas, K., & Redmond, P. (2023). Skills-displacing technological change and its impact on jobs: challenging technological alarmism?. *Economics of Innovation and New Technology*, 32(3), 370-392.
- Meier, C., Sachs, S., Stutz, C., & McSorley, V. (2017). Establishing a digital leadership barometer for small and medium enterprises (SME). *Proceedings of the Make Learn and TIIM International Conference*, Lublin, 103-109.
- Mert, G. (2021). Dijital dünyada yeni bir boyut: Dijital liderlik. *Satın Alma Dergisi*, 97, 50-51.
- Miller, C. (2018). Digital leadership: Using the internet and the social media to improve the lives, well-being, and circumstances of others. *Journal of Family and Consumer Sciences*, 110(1), 47-49.
- Mullins, J. L. (2005). *Management and organizational behavior* (7th Ed.). Pearson Education.
- Muniroh, M., Hamidah, H., & Abdullah, T. (2021). Indicator analysis of employee performance based on the effect of digital leadership, digital culture, organizational learning, and innovation. *Proceedings of the 5th International Indonesia Naval Technology College STTAL Postgraduate Conference on Maritime Science and Technology*
- Mysirlaki, S., & Paraskeva, F. (2020). Emotional intelligence and transformational leadership in virtual teams: Lessons from MMOGs. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 41(4), 551-566.
- Oberer, B., & Erkollar, A. (2018). Leadership 4.0: Digital leaders in the age of industry 4.0. *International Journal of Organizational Leadership*, 7(4), 404-412.
- Ordu, A., & Nayır, F. (2021). Dijital liderlik nedir? Bir tanım önerisi. *E-Uluslararası Eğitim Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 12(3), 68-81.
- Özmen, Ö. N. T., Eriş, E. D., & Süral Özer, P. (2020). Dijital liderlik çalışmalarına bir bakış. *Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi İİBF Dergisi*, 25(1), 57-69.
- Park, J., Kim, S., Kim, S. D., & Kim, I. G. (2021). The effects of golf coaches' authentic leadership and transformational leadership on leader-member exchange and athlete's perceived performance. *Psychologia*, 63(1), 73-92.
- Pasolong, H., Nilna, M., & Justina, A. J. (2021). Digital leadership in facing challenges in the era industrial revolution 4.0. *Webology*, 18, 975-990.
- Pellegrini, E. K., & Scandura, T. A. (2008). Paternalistic leadership: A review and agenda for future research. *Journal of Management*, 34(3), 566-593.

- Promsri, C. (2019). The developing model of digital leadership for a successful digital transformation. *GPII-International Journal of Business Management*, 2(8), 01-08.
- Radulescu, V., Anghel, L. D., Cetina, I., Cruceru, A. F., & Onișor, L. F. (2020). Job satisfaction and services business sustainability: Empirical study using role theory. *Economic Computation & Economic Cybernetics Studies & Research*, 54(4), 55–70.
- Robbins, S. P. (2001). *Organizational behavior* (9th Ed.). Prentice-Hall.
- Rudito, P., & Sinaga, M. F. (2017). *Digital mastery*. Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Sabuncuoğlu, Z. (2001). *İşletmelerde halkla ilişkiler*. Ezgi Kitabevi Yayınları.
- Shah, S. S., & Patki, S. M. (2020). Getting traditionally rooted Indian leadership to embrace digital leadership: Challenges and way forward with reference to LMX. *Leadership Education and Personal Interdisciplinary Journal*, 2(1), 29–40.
- Sheninger, E. (2014). Pillars of digital leadership. *International Center for Leadership in Education*, 1-4.
- Sow, M., & Aborbie, S. (2018). Impact of leadership on digital transformation. *Business and Economic Research*, 8(3), 139-148
- Spector, P. E. (1985). Measurement of human service staff satisfaction: Development of the Job Satisfaction Survey. *American Journal of Community Psychology*, 13(6), 693-713.
- Srimata, T., Niyamabha, A., Wichitputchraporn, W., Piyapimonsit, C., Prachongchit, S., & Koedsuwan, S. (2019). A causal model of digital leadership and school climates with work engagement as mediator affecting effectiveness of private schools in Bangkok, Thailand. *Asian Administration & Management Review*, 2(2), 290–297.
- Statt, D. (2004). *The Routledge dictionary of business management* (3rd Ed.). Routledge.
- Sulistiana, I. N., & Sri Darma, G. (2023). Digital Leadership, Work-Life Balance, Compensation, Job Satisfaction, and Employee Engagement. *Quantitative Economics and Management Studies*, 4(5), 981-993.
- Şahin, Ç. Ç., Avcı, Y. E., & Amık, S. (2020). Dijital liderlik algısının metaforlar yoluyla incelenmesi. *Elektronik Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 19(73), 271-288.
- Şimşir, İ., & Seyran, F. (2020). İş tatmininin önemi ve etkileri. *Meyad Akademi*, 1(1), 25-42.
- Tanucan, Jem Cloyd M., Crislee V. Negrado, & Grace N. Malaga. "Digital leadership of school heads and job satisfaction of teachers in the Philippines during the pandemic." *International journal of learning, teaching and educational research* 21.10 (2022): 1-18.
- Teichmann, S., & Hüning, C. (2018). Digital leadership. *Disruption und Transformation Management* (23-42). Springer Gabler, Wiesbaden.
- Temelkova, M. (2018). Skills for digital leadership - prerequisite for developing high-tech economy. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences*, 7(12), 50–74.
- Tengilimoğlu, D. (2005). Hizmet işletmelerinde liderlik davranışları ile iş doyumunu arasındaki ilişkinin belirlenmesine yönelik bir araştırma. *Ticaret ve Turizm Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 1, 23-45.
- Toduk, Y. (2017). Dijital liderler nasıl olmalı? *Hürriyet*. <http://www.hurriyet.com.tr/ik-yeni-ekonomi/dijital-liderler-nasil-olmeli-40492744> (Online Access: 17.04.2018).
- Topçuoğlu, E., Kobanoğlu, M. S., Kaygın, E., Karafakıoğlu, E., Uygungil Erdoğan, S., Turan Torun, B., & Oktaysoy, O. (2023). The improving role of digital leadership in the impact of social loafing on job performance. *International Journal of Organizational Leadership*, 22–40.
- Ugboro, I., & Obeng, K. (2000). Top management leadership, employee empowerment, job satisfaction, and customer satisfaction in total quality management organizations: An empirical study. *Journal of Quality Management*, 5, 247-272.
- Üçüncü, K. (2016). *İş tatmini ve motivasyon*. Trabzon.
- Webster's II: New Riverside University Dictionary. (1994). Riverside Publishing Company.

Westerman, G., Bonnet, D., & McAfee, A. (2014). *Leading digital: Turning technology into business transformation*. Harvard Business Review Press.

Wilson III, E. J. (2004). Leadership in the digital age. In G. R. Goethals, G. Sorenson, & J. M. Burns (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Leadership*, (Vol. 4, 858-861). Sage.

Winston, B. E., & Patterson, K. (2006). An integrative definition of leadership. *International Journal of Leadership Studies*, 1(2), 6-66.

Yalçıntaş, M., & Eren, F. (2017). Hizmetkar liderlik ile iş tatmini arasındaki ilişki: Bir havayolu şirketi örneği. *Uluslararası İktisadi ve İdari İncelemeler Dergisi*, 851-864.

Yıkılmaz, İ. (2021). Covid-19 pandemic as a digital transformation catalyst. In M. Meciar & H. Şimşek (Eds.), *The social and economic impact of Covid-19*, (119-138). IJOPEC Publication.

Yılmaz, H., & Karahan, A. (2010). Liderlik davranışı, örgütsel yaratıcılık ve iş gören performansı arasındaki ilişkilerin incelenmesi: Uşak'ta bir araştırma. *Yönetim ve Ekonomi Dergisi*, 17(2), 145-158.

Yusuf, M., Satia, H., Bernardianto, R., Nurhasanah, N., Irwani, I., & Setyoko, P. (2023). Exploring the role of digital leadership and digital transformation on the performance of the public sector organizations. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 7(4), 1983-1990.

Zeike, S., Bradbury, K., Lindert, L., & Pfaff, H. (2019). Digital leadership skills and associations with psychological well-being. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(14).

Zhu, Y. (2013). A review of job satisfaction. *Asian Social Science*, 9(1), 293.

Zhou, H., Jin, M., & Ma, Q. (2015). Remedy for work stress: The impact and mechanism of ethical leadership. *Central European Journal of Public Health*, 23(2), 176-180.

Zupancic, T., Herneoja, A., Schoonjans, Y., & Achten, H. (2018). A research framework of digital leadership. *Proceedings of the 36th eCAADe Conference*, Łódź, Poland, 1, 641-646.